

Interview schedule

Welcomes

Introductions and thanks for meeting with us.

Our short preamble:

These questions are a starting off point. There are no right or wrong answers. We're interested in your stories so please feel very free to tell us what you'd like to tell us about. Please also feel free to show us any photographs or pictures or other materials that you see as relevant. Please do ask for clarification if a question does not make sense.

Ethics preamble:

You can get in touch with us by email at any time.

We will only use your stories and experiences for the purposes of the research project.

You are welcome to choose a pseudonym (a made up name that we use to refer to you) or we can choose one for you if you would like.

Reminders about the right to withdraw from the study at any time.

Do you have any questions that you would like to ask at this stage?

Initial notes

Date _____

Time of interview _____

Name of participant _____

Participant number _____

Year of birth _____

Email address _____

Children at home during the lockdowns _____

County _____

Pseudonym? _____

General narrative invitation:

Would you like to tell us about your experiences of educating your child(ren) during the covid pandemic?

Prompts arranged by theme:

[Place and Space theme]

Where did home-schooling take place? What did the workspaces look like? Do you have photos from the time?

Can you describe/draw the relevant spaces?

(Photographs?)

What resources did you use?

(And questions below regarding links with others)

[Time and temporality theme]

Would you like to tell us about a typical day?

Did you have a schedule from school?

Did you have any routines?

How did home-schooling fit around other commitments?

What are the most memorable moments from home-schooling during the lockdown?

Would you like to tell us about your best and worse experiences?

[Energy and Action]

Describe your approach to home schooling.

Did you teach your children things? Did you follow the activities suggested by the school?

Perhaps you have photos or school work or other documents from this time that you might like to share with us?

How did you try to make the work accessible?

What were your aims when home-schooling? What do you hope for, for your children?

Did you feel linked to others during this time?/How did you make links with others during this time?

Did the school plan virtual catch up or online lessons of any kind?

Was social media important to you? School learning platforms?

Towards the end

Is there anything else we haven't covered?

Do you have any questions that you'd like to ask?

Ending

Thank you for your time. We're very grateful.

If you do think of anything else you want to say about anything we've talked about or want to ask any questions then please do email us. (kes709@alumni.bham.ac.uk)

Field notes

